

Article

Effect of Pre-reduction of Manganese Ore by Hydrogen on Its Smelting Behavior and Interaction with Stable Oxides

Authors:

- **Pankaj Kumar** - NTNU Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Department of Materials Science and Engineering, Faculty of Natural Sciences, Resources, Energy & Environment research group.
- **Jafar Safarian** - NTNU Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Department of Materials Science and Engineering, Faculty of Natural Sciences, Resources, Energy & Environment research group.

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